

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Caveolin-1 (UniProt ID: Q03135) for use in western blot

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Abstract

Caveolin-1 is the main component of caveolae that form at the plasma membrane and plays a multitude of roles in cellular processes like endocytosis, cholesterol transport, and signal transduction. Here we have characterized seventeen Caveolin-1 commercial antibodies for western blot using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

Q03135, *CAV1*, Caveolin-1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

The *CAV1* gene encodes a 21 kDa named Caveolin-1. This protein contains a central scaffolding domain (residues D82–R101) involved in membrane, protein and cholesterol binding, a transmembrane domain (residues L102–I134), and a C-terminal oligomer–oligomer interaction domain ((residues K135–I178) (1). Caveolin-1 is the main component of caveolae, plasma membrane structures that are rich in cholesterol and sphingolipids, and involved in cellular vesicular trafficking (2). Caveolin-1 is a player in multiple cellular signaling pathways and regulates cell proliferation, differentiation, migration and survival (3). Evidence shows the involvement of Caveolin-1 in neurodegenerative diseases (2, 4) and cancer (5).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (6). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein (6). Here we characterized seventeen commercial Caveolin-1 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of Caveolin-1 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (7) and in Table 4 of this data note (6).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (8, 9). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (10). The U-87 MG expresses the *CAV1* transcript at $9.2 \log_2$ TPM+1. A *CAV1* KO U-87 MG cell line was obtained from Abcam (Table 1). Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the U-87 MG does not carry mutations in the *CAV1* that could affect antibody–epitope binding.

All seventeen antibodies were screened by western blot using WT and *CAV1* KO protein lysates ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with the different Caveolin-1 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

In conclusion, we have screened seventeen commercial antibodies in western blot by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human U-87 MG WT and *CAV1* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 4 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in this application (10). High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect Caveolin-1 were identified.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available Caveolin-1 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in Caveolin-1, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. Caveolin-1 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (6). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines, primary and secondary antibodies used in this study are listed in Table 1, 2, and 3, respectively. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (11, 12). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

U-87 MG WT and *CAV1* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 5% 2-Mercaptoethanol (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 125472500) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Data availability*Underlying data*

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab278079	CVCL_0022	U-87 MG	WT
Abcam	ab306811	CVCL_D1RU	U-87 MG	CAV1 KO

Table 2: Summary of the Caveolin-1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab17052*	1002709-4	AB_443609	monoclonal	7C8	mouse	0.10	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab192869**	1001906-8	AB_3068592	recombinant mono	EPR15554	rabbit	0.65	Wb, IP, IF
Abcam	ab227636**	GR3217468-2	AB_3068593	recombinant mono	SP43	rabbit	NA	IHC
Abcam	ab32577**	1033023-10	AB_725987	recombinant mono	E249	rabbit	0.12	Wb, IP, IF, IHC
ABclonal	A19006**	3561620007	AB_2862498	recombinant mono	ARC50848	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IHC
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NB100-615*	B15	AB_10003431	monoclonal	7C8	mouse	1.00	Wb, IP, IF, IHC
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	AF5736	CDWR0122121	AB_10571370	polyclonal	-	goat	0.20	Wb, IHC
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB5736*	CCPF0520121	AB_2071999	monoclonal	7C8	mouse	0.50	Wb, IF
Cell Signaling Technology	3267**	9	AB_2275453	recombinant mono	D46G3	rabbit	0.69	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX100205	39274	AB_1240559	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IP, IF, IHC
MilliporeSigma	ZRB1602**	Q3776373	AB_3698367	recombinant mono	1D10	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IP, IF, IHC
Proteintech	66067-1-Ig*	10004352	AB_11043343	monoclonal	6C2B2	mouse	1.30	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA3-600*	YA365993	AB_779568	monoclonal	7C8	mouse	0.00	Wb, IP, IF, IHC
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-32020**	YE3913385	AB_2809314	recombinant mono	SZ02-01	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF, IHC
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-45045*	YE3913389B	AB_2931499	monoclonal	19-D6	mouse	2.00	Wb, IF, IHC
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-45053*	YE3913380A	AB_2931507	monoclonal	A3E4	mouse	2.00	Wb, IHC
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA1-064	YA352571	AB_2072027	Polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	WB, IP, IF

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, IHC=immunohistochemistry, *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Thermo Fisher Scientific	HRP-Donkey Anti-Goat Antibody (H+L)	A15999	AB_2534673	polyclonal	1.0	0.5

Table 4: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in western blot

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Figure 1: Caveolin-1 antibody screening by western blot (1/2)

Figure 1: Caveolin-1 antibody screening by western blot (2/2)

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Caveolin-1 antibody screening by western blot.

20 µg of lysates from U-87 MG WT and *CAV1* KO were used for western blot. Samples were prepared by adding LDS to 1x final and 5% of 2-Mercaptoethanol and boiling for 10 min prior to immunoblotting with the indicated Caveolin-1 antibodies. Protein migration was performed using 10% Bis-Tris gels with MES-SDS buffer. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab17052* at 1/500, ab192869** at 1/10 000, ab227636** at 1/500, ab32577** at 1/1000, A19006** at 1/5000, NB100-615* at 1/1000, AF5736 at 1/1000, MAB5736* at 1/500, 3267** at 1/1000, GTX100205 at 1/500, ZRB1602** at 1/1000, 66067-1-Ig* at 1/2000, MA3-600* at 1/500, MA5-32020** at 1/1000, MA5-45045* at 1/500, MA5-45053* at 1/1000, and PA1-064 at 1/500. Predicted band size: 20.4 kDa. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.